

An integrated renewable energy system for the decarbonization of a laying hens farm in Central Greece

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Abstract. Intensive livestock farming heavily relies on fossil fuels, leading to significant greenhouse gas emissions, particularly for maintaining optimal environmental conditions in livestock buildings. Furthermore, transitioning to Renewable Energy Sources (RES) is crucial for the EU's livestock sector. In the present work, a pilot study at the Agricultural University of Athens aimed to decarbonize an experimental laying hen's facility while improving animal welfare. The farm was upgraded with a RES system, including an innovative heat pump (HP) for climate control and a solar photovoltaic (PV) system for power generation. A sensor-based monitoring system collected data on the system's performance and indoor conditions over an extended period. The study focused on the impact of the RES system during summer and winter periods. Preliminary results indicate that the installed HP enhances animal welfare by maintaining adequate indoor air temperatures during heat waves, eliminating mortality. When combined with the PV system, it significantly reduces electricity consumption from the grid by 20-23%, leading to a CO₂-eq reduction of around 688 and 314 kgCO₂-eq in summer and winter, respectively. During the testing and finetuning period, the HP Seasonal Coefficient of Performance reached 2.42 and 3.65 in summer and winter, respectively. These findings offer valuable insights into the potential for scaling up RES integration in commercial livestock facilities, highlighting the benefits for energy efficiency and animal welfare.

Keywords: Climate resilience, Energy-smart agriculture, Fossil fuels, Heat pump, Photovoltaic panels.

1 Introduction

Intensive livestock systems are energy-intensive and primarily rely on fossil fuels [1]. This high consumption of non-renewable energy conflicts with policies of several countries that promote a more environmentally friendly agricultural sector [2]. To support the transition towards more sustainable livestock production, new energy-efficient solutions and technologies have been tested in the very last few years, with a special focus on climate control systems [3]. While some studies focused on the improvement of the conventional systems, others are proposing a paradigm shift, by implementing innovative solutions, such as the Heat Pump (HP) technology. HP is a Renewable Energy Sources (RES) technology, promising for the livestock sector due to its high energy efficiency and capability to cope with heat waves by providing mechanical cooling. Despite these advantages, the application of HPs in livestock houses is still limited and few studies have focused on this topic. Experimental studies of HPs installed in pig houses highlighted decreases in primary energy consumption, operating energy costs [4], and carbon footprint [5]. A comparative analysis between a poultry house equipped with an HP and a conventional one highlighted decreased poultry mortality and lower operational costs when the HP is used [6]. A numerical analysis focusing on an HP integrated into a poultry house revealed a high Coefficient of Performance (COP) and Energy Efficiency Ratio (EER) [7]. However, further studies are necessary to enhance the adoption of HP technologies in livestock buildings. It is essential to gain a better understanding of the actual performances of HP systems in real operating conditions, while also considering the presence of auxiliary equipment and the integration with photovoltaic (PV) panels.

This work aims to expand the current body of knowledge on the integration of HPs in livestock buildings by providing information on their actual performance under real operating conditions. For this reason, a dataset collected from an experimental poultry house equipped with an air-to-air HP combined with a PV system is analysed to provide insights regarding the indoor climate conditions, the HP performance, and the energy consumption.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 The case study

The laying hen house. The case study is the experimental hen house of the Agricultural University of Athens (Greece). It is a fully enclosed building of around 45 m² (154 m³) with 3-tier enriched colonies, where hens are farmed from the 18th to their 80th week of age. Currently, it houses 330 hens with an average liveweight of 1.8 kg. The walls are made of stone ($U = 1.66 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and a tile roof is insulated with expanded polyethylene ($U = 0.45 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Lighting is provided by programmable LED strips capable of simulating dusk-dawn conditions. The house is equipped with a sensor-based smart monitoring and control system (i.e., energy meter and environmental monitoring sensors) which communicates with the HP.

The climate control system. To enhance animal welfare, the desirable conditions inside the house are achieved using an innovative Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system, with a 10 kW water-to-air HP at its core. The HP provides the necessary heating and cooling loads. It operates with R407C refrigerant, and its main components are a screw-type Copeland ZR48K3E-TFD compressor, coupled with a Variable Frequency Drive (VFD), and two heat exchangers (i.e., plate, fin-and-tube), and an adiabatic dry cooler. Two fans have also been incorporated to supply the house with fresh or conditioned air (inlet fan: $2.0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ liveweight), inside the HP unit, and ventilate (exhaust fan: $2.2\text{-}15.0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ liveweight) the house. Finally, two pumps are used to circulate water between the HP and the dry cooler, and the HP and the recuperator. To further decarbonize the system, a 9 kW_p photovoltaic (PV) system was also installed. When the PV production exceeds the energy needs of the hen house, the excess power is supplied to nearby buildings.

2.2 Data collection and analysis

The case study was equipped with a sensor network connected via a gateway to a cloud platform, where data are stored with a 5-minute time step. The environmental sensors monitored the indoor (θ_{in}) and outdoor (θ_{out}) air temperature, relative humidity (ϕ_{in} , ϕ_{out}), as well as the outdoor global solar radiation (I_{sol}). Indoor conditions were monitored using three temperature and humidity sensors placed along the colony. The recorded values were then averaged to provide a single representative value for both θ_{in} and ϕ_{in} . Outdoor weather conditions were monitored by a weather station near the farm. The energy meters monitored the overall laying hen house energy consumption and the production of the PV. The power input for fans and pumps is obtained by considering their nominal power and efficiency. For inverter fans, the load (capacity) percentage was taken into account as well. To assess the performance of the HP, the refrigerant pressure was monitored before (low-pressure section) and after (high-pressure section) the compressor. Knowing these pressures, the evaporation and condensation temperature of the refrigerant was calculated as follows:

$$\theta = -0.0002*p^4 + 0.015*p^3 - 0.4768*p^2 + 8.9806*p - 27.279 \quad (1)$$

where θ and p are the refrigerant saturation temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and pressure (bar), respectively. To calculate θ_{ev} , the refrigerant low pressure (suction line) is inserted into Eq. (1), while θ_{cd} is calculated using the high pressure (liquid line). Eq. (1) was obtained as a polynomial regression on a range of different refrigerant pressures and temperatures calculated using EES software [8]. Since R407C is a zeotropic fluid, the temperatures have been calculated in the state of saturated vapour. Knowing θ_{ev} and θ_{cd} , the HP power input (\dot{W}) and the cooling capacity (\dot{Q}_c) can be estimated in kW using the compressor polynomial of Eq. (2), as provided by the manufacturer [9]. The polynomial coefficients ($C0$ to $C9$), for each parameter, are reported in Table 1.

$$\dot{W}, \text{ or } \dot{Q}_c = C0 + C1*\theta_{ev} + C2*\theta_{cd} + C3*\theta_{ev}^2 + C4*\theta_{ev}*\theta_{cd} + C5*\theta_{cd}^2 + \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\dots + C6*\theta_{ev}^3 + C7*\theta_{cd}*\theta_{ev}^2 + C8*\theta_{ev}*\theta_{cd}^2 + C9*\theta_{cd}^3$$

Table 1. Copeland ZR48K3E-TFD compressor polynomial coefficients [9].

Parameter	C0	C1	C2	C3	C4
Cooling capacity	13.1924	0.491268	-0.07855	0.007447	-0.00214
Power input	0.261666	-0.03545	0.082887	-0.00076	0.001243
Parameter	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9
Cooling capacity	-0.00042	4.01E-05	-4.3E-05	-1.5E-05	2.58E-07
Power input	-0.00126	-6.5E-06	1.38E-05	-1.2E-05	1.61E-05

Finally, the heating capacity (\dot{Q}_H) and COP are calculated as the sum of the power input and cooling capacity, and as the heating, or cooling, capacity over the power input.

3 Results and Discussion

The data analysed during two characteristic periods -summer and winter- are presented and discussed next. During both periods, the HP operated either in cooling mode (summer) or heating mode (winter).

3.1 Indoor climate conditions and HP performance

Even though the summer of 2023 was one of the warmest of the last years in Greece, the HP effectively regulated indoor temperature. Figure 1 presents results for the period from the 20th to the 30th of July. The HP was set to maintain θ_{in} within a deadband of 25 ± 2 °C because this temperature is considered the upper limit of thermal comfort of laying hens, which was achieved for a satisfactory part of the period. The HP would turn off when the indoor temperature reached 23 °C, but due to the high thermal loads, it was not possible during this period. However, even under extreme conditions (θ_{out} up to 46 °C), the indoor temperature did not exceed 30 °C. The flock experienced heat stress during the day, but lower θ_{in} during the night allowed for easing. The HP provided the expected cooling loads, and the COP was above 2 most of the time. Poorer HP performance and lower \dot{Q}_C can be observed in Figure 1 due to suboptimal defrost cycle programming.

Figure 1. Temperatures variation and HP performance between 20-30/07/2023.

During December, θ_{in} was maintained within a deadband of 20 ± 2 °C to avoid unnecessary HP operation for heating. The HP effectively maintained θ_{in} between 18 and 21 °C, even when θ_{out} reached 3 °C. However, several fluctuations of θ_{in} can be noticed during this period. Those fluctuations can be explained by considering that the heat loads needed to maintain θ_{in} within the deadband are lower compared to the cooling loads. Hence, when the HP is activated, θ_{in} immediately reaches the upper limit of the deadband (21 °C) and decreases due to the low values of θ_{out} . The fluctuations also affect the COP and \dot{Q}_H due to the continuous oscillation of the temperature difference between the outdoor and indoor environment, which affects the HP performance. As can be observed in Figure 2, the COP exceeded 3 throughout the period. Studying a 30-day period for each case, the Seasonal COP (SCOP) for summer was 2.42, while for winter was 3.65.

Figure 2. Temperature variation and HP performance between 10-20/12/2023.

3.2 Energy consumption

Table 2 provides a breakdown of the energy consumption of each component of the system. As expected, HP's consumption was much higher during summer. Although the HP operates more frequently during summer, the unit fan has comparable consumption, because of its function as a ventilator. It must be noted that, although gas concentrations were low during both periods, high levels of dust were observed. To mitigate this issue, a much higher-capacity fan (2.38 kW – 10,210 m³ h⁻¹, instead of 0.46 kW – 1,610 m³ h⁻¹) was installed in autumn. This explains the considerable difference between summer and winter exhaust fan consumption. Water pumps and LEDs consumed approximately the same amount of energy during both periods.

Table 2. Energy consumption and PV production between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).

Period	HP compressor (kWh)	Unit fan (kWh)	Exhaust fan (kWh)	Dry cooler fan (kWh)	Water pumps (kWh)	Lights (kWh)
Summer	2,627.05	196.55	268.19	468.71	439.72	31.01
Winter	307.45	153.00	1,357.17	69.36	470.81	31.72

The total amount of electrical energy consumed by the facility as well as that produced by the PVs, are summarized for both periods in Table 3. The total energy used during summer was around 68% higher than in winter since the compressor alone used about 8.5 times more energy to cover the high cooling needs. The performance of the PV system was evaluated using the Self-Sufficiency (SS) and the Self-Consumption (SC) as metrics, as reported in [10], and considering a 5-minute time step. In both studied periods, the SS of the system was around 20%. By contrast, the SC was higher during summer, as almost all the PV energy was used on-site to meet the high energy demand for cooling. During winter, the lower energy consumption allowed for exporting part of the PV energy to the grid (local users), reducing the SC to around 86%. Considering the IPCC emission factor for electrical energy for Greece (0.76 tCO_{2-eq} MWh⁻¹) [11] and the actual self-consumed PV energy, it is estimated that the emissions of 688 kgCO_{2-eq} and 314 kgCO_{2-eq} were avoided during the course of the analysed summer (20/07-19/08) and winter (01/12-30/12) periods, respectively.

Table 3. Energy and HP performance-related data between 20/07-19/08/2023 (summer) and 01/12-30/12/2023 (winter).

Period (mode)	Total electricity used (kWh)	Total electricity produced (kWh)	Self-Sufficiency (%)	Self-Consumption (%)
Summer (cooling)	4,031.23	908.50	22.54	99.70
Winter (heating)	2,389.51	482.71	20.20	85.60

A possible solution aimed at further decarbonizing the system could be to increase the peak power of the PV system. However, this solution should be carefully studied due to potential mismatches between power demand and PV supply. In Figure 3, the trends of

power consumption and PV production are shown for a summer (Figure 3a) and winter (Figure 3b) week. During summer, the energy demand is high (around 6 kW) and almost constant during daytime and nighttime. In winter, the energy demand is usually lower (around 3 kW), but significant spikes (up to 8 kW) occur in the afternoon. Consequently, an increase in PV peak power could be beneficial in both periods because there is still room for increasing the SS. However, the mismatch during winter and the constant load during summer suggest the possibility of evaluating the integration of electrical energy storage to fill the gap between energy demand and PV energy availability.

Figure 3. Power consumption and photovoltaic power generation during an indicative summer (a) and winter (b) week.

Since installing a larger PV system to cover the total electricity needs (in this case, nearly four times larger) is often limited by space and budget constraints, incorporating a battery storage system is a viable alternative. In the present study, a battery system with a capacity of 10 kWh (or 15-20 kWh to account for potential future needs) could maximize SC.

4 Conclusions and future work

The results obtained during the first testing months of the integrated RES systems operation largely appear satisfactory, with SCOP of 2.42 and 3.65 in summer and winter, respectively and a considerable decrease of greenhouse gas emissions, quantifiable in 688 and 314 kgCO_{2-eq} for a summer and a winter month respectively. The system significantly lowered indoor air temperatures during heat waves, positively impacting both animal welfare (with the mortality rate decreasing by approximately 27.95%) and productivity. These temperature reductions were achieved without increasing relative humidity, as it happens using adiabatic cooling systems, representing an additional advantage of the analysed systems. Future experiments should specifically focus on integrating more effectively the HP and ventilation systems to enhance indoor air quality

by minimising dust accumulation. The greatest challenge in this study was likely the selected air conditioning system using channels, which was primarily dictated by space limitations and proved suboptimal. Future research should explore experimentation in both purpose-built small experimental facilities and contemporary commercial ones. Another relevant aspect that should be analysed to enhance the adoption of HPs in the livestock sector is the sizing of HPs also when integrated with conventional systems. While international standards and national regulations clearly define the design conditions for other building types, for livestock houses this information is not available. Until now, it was not a priority because cooling was provided with forced ventilation. However, to encourage technicians and practitioners to shift toward more innovative solutions, the establishment of standards and guidelines is of the foremost importance.

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